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“The impact of the preclinical online Flipped Classroom (FC) on the critical thinking, group working and independent learning abilities from student's perspective”

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“Promoting online communication skills in undergraduate medical students in response of COVID-19 – Tele-OSCE”

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#SC13: SC - Teaching & Learning and COVID-19 1**#SC13.2 The impact of the preclinical online Flipped Classroom (FC) on the critical thinking, group working and independent learning abilities from students' perspective (9179)****Date of Presentation:** 29 August 2021**Time of Presentation:** 16:15 to 16:30**AUTHOR(S):****Tsisana Lomashvili, Petre Shotadze Tbilisi Medical Academy (TMA), Georgia***

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ABSTRACT:

Background: FC gained special interest during the last, COVID-19 pandemics year, among the medical educators in order to improve online learning opportunities through increased student engagement. All the three Universities involved in this research are in the process of piloting the online FC method. This study was aimed to find out the impact of online FC method on the development of critical thinking, independent working and group working abilities from preclinical students perspective.

Summary of Work: Students from the three institutions were involved in FC format teaching in basic subjects. During the online FC sessions Google Meet and Zoom brake out room platforms were used. Structured written and oral interviews were performed with three focus groups of students from the three institutions; a questionnaire with five-point unipolar response Likert scale was created. The survey was performed on Survey Monkey platform. The number of participants in the survey - 392 (53%), from total number of 740 exposed to the method. Quantitative analysis of the survey data was performed using IBM SPSS statistics 22.0 program.

Summary of Results: The weight averages on Likert scale for competencies are: for critical thinking 3.8 ± 1.06 , for independent working skills 3.7 ± 1.16 and for team player 3.9 ± 1.1 The highest weight averages were for all three competencies in II and IV semesters, with no significant differences across the semesters ($p < 0.05$). The Ratios of more positive, more negative and neutral responses for each competency on Likert scale: critical thinking - 65%, 12%, 23%; independent working abilities - 60%, 16%, 24%; group working/team player - 67%, 11%, 22 % respectively.

Discussion and Conclusions: Students regard the online FC format important in development of critical thinking, independent learning and group working. Results will facilitate further implementation of FC in online and off-line settings.

Take-home Messages: FC should be further promoted at preclinical level in MD curriculum.